

INTEGRATION OF DAMAS ROUTES WITH BUS STATIONS

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Abstract. *Integration of Damas routes with bus stops will make the transport system more efficient and convenient. This integration ensures uninterrupted and fast communication for travelers, facilitates the transition between routes, and saves time. Also, through integration, it is possible to regulate passenger traffic and reduce the load on the city's internal transport system. This approach improves the quality of transport services, coordinates intercity and intra-city traffic, and contributes to ensuring environmental safety. This study analyzes the methods of effective communication between routes and stops.*

Keywords: *Damas, routes, bus stops, integration, transport system, passenger flow*

Introduction. The public transport system in the city of Andijan is one of the most important means of meeting the population's demand for movement. Currently, several modes of transport operate in the city, including: large and medium-capacity buses, minibuses, taxi services, and especially the widely used Damas minibuses. Together, these tools form the basis of the city's transport infrastructure.

In particular, Damas cars are distinguished by their compactness, maneuverability, and convenient movement on narrow and densely populated streets. Therefore, they are widely used on short-distance routes within the city, within mahallas and neighborhoods. However, in current practice, it is observed that these vehicles are not sufficiently coordinated with the main bus routes. As a result, problems arise such as improper distribution of passenger traffic, repetition of vehicle traffic (duplicate trips), traffic congestion, and congestion.

In addition, the movement of all vehicles entering the city center along a single route, against the background of the limited infrastructure intended for them, causes negative environmental and economic consequences. In particular, there are cases of urban air pollution, increased fuel consumption, excessive time loss for passengers, and increased operating costs of vehicles.

Methodology. In this regard, the need to review the public transport movement system, especially the integration of Damas cars with bus stops operating in the city, is

becoming a pressing issue. This will serve not only to regulate traffic flow, but also to form a convenient, efficient, and cost-effective transport system for passengers.

Connecting routes in the city public transport system are understood as separate routes that ensure easy and quick exchange of passengers between several main transport routes - for example, buses, Damas, and other types of public transport, delivering them to their destinations with minimal time and costs. These routes serve as a separate coordinating link in the transport system and ensure the continuity of movement within the city, the functional harmony of networks. Connecting routes, as a rule, play a key role in increasing the efficiency of the public transport system, connecting strategically important areas, such as large settlements, industrial and trade zones, educational and medical institutions, railway stations, markets, and administrative centers. Such routes play an important role in regulating passenger traffic, reducing traffic congestion, and ensuring coordination between routes. Especially, the presence of connecting routes at the intersection points of routes between small-capacity vehicles, such as buses and Damas, provides passengers with convenience, reliability, and time savings when changing vehicles.

In this chapter, this issue of integration is deeply analyzed, existing problems are highlighted, and a new systemic approach is developed based on the proposed transport model.

Analysis of the current situation

In the city of Andijan, most Damas routes are organized independently, and they are formed not in connection with bus stops, but at the request of passengers. This leads to the following problems:

- Uncoordinated schedule between routes;
- Buses and Damases move in the same directions;
- Accumulation of excess vehicles in the city center;
- Difficulties for passengers when moving between vehicles.

Route Names	Distance (km)
Gulshan MFY - Hospital No. 2	15.6
Airport - Combined area	14.
Bostan mahalla - Old City	6.
Pistamozor - Stream	7.5
Impartial - World Market	9.5
Kholis - Agricultural University	13.5
Old Town - Khrabek	14.
Zangi Bobo - Old City (via ADU)	13.
Total	93.1

Necessity of integration

To increase the efficiency of public transport, it is necessary to integrate Damas routes with large bus stops. Integration serves the following purposes:

- Collecting passengers from local areas by Damas and transporting them to the main transport hubs - that is, to large stops or terminal points (conventionally, the "feeder system" or "collecting traffic" function).
- And buses carry out the transportation of large passenger flows over long distances along the main routes.
- This system optimizes the number of routes, reduces total traffic, and saves time for passengers.

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